

Совершенствование процесса обучения иностранному языку младших школьников с использованием сюжетно-ролевой игры

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. В современных условиях образовательной реформы возрастают требования к коммуникативной компетенции. Использование сюжетно-ролевых игр в учебной деятельности младших школьников отвечает актуальным педагогическим запросам и способствует эффективному развитию их иноязычной компетенции. *Целью настоящего исследования* является анализ и оценка метода сюжетно-ролевой игры как средства повышения мотивационной активности и повышения качества усвоения иностранного языка младшими школьниками.

Материалы и методы. Для реализации поставленной цели использовался комплексный подход: 1) анализ научной литературы, который позволил выявить текущие тенденции и пробелы в исследовании данной проблемы; 2) анкетирование 20 учителей и 40 студентов, проведенное с целью сбора эмпирических данных о практическом опыте; 3) экспериментальное исследование с участием 54 младших школьников, направленное на проверку гипотезы и получение объективных данных в условиях контролируемого эксперимента. Для оценки эффективности проведенного эксперимента применялся критерий хи-квадрат Пирсона, который позволил статистически проверить значимость полученных различий.

Результаты исследования. В рамках экспериментального исследования был апробирован специально разработанный набор заданий и упражнений, ориентированных на формирование иноязычной компетенции, выполненных в игровой форме. Применение данного комплекса способствовало значительному улучшению лексико-грамматических навыков у учащихся третьих классов в процессе изучения иностранного языка положительно повлиял на развитие их коммуникативной компетенции ($\chi^2 = 6,290$; $p < 0,05$).

Заключение. Исследование подтвердило, что сюжетно-ролевая игра, объединяя элементы реалистичных ситуаций и игровых ролей, создает условия для осознанного и осмысленного усвоения языка, что особенно важно для младших школьников. Практическая значимость использования сюжетно-ролевых игр подтверждается их способностью формировать речевые умения, социально-коммуникативные навыки и развивать личностные качества детей, делая процесс обучения более увлекательным и результативным.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

сюжетно-ролевая игра, обучение иностранному языку, младшие школьники, лексико-грамматические навыки, иноязычная компетенция, мотивация

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Role-Play Games as a Means of Enhancing Foreign Language Acquisition of Primary School Students

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. In the context of contemporary educational reforms, the demands on communicative competence have increased. The implementing of role-playing activities in the educational process in primary schools meets current pedagogical demands and contributes to the effective development of their foreign language competence. *The aim of this study* is to analyze and evaluate the method of role-playing games as a means to enhance motivational activity and improve the quality of foreign language acquisition among younger students.

Materials and Methods. To achieve the stated objective, a comprehensive approach was employed consisting of: 1) analysis of scientific literature, which allowed identification of current trends and gaps in the study of the problem; 2) a surveys of 20 teachers and 40 students aimed at collecting empirical data on practical experience; 3) an experimental study involving 54 elementary school students aimed at testing hypotheses and obtaining objective data under controlled conditions. The effectiveness of the conducted experiment was evaluated using Pearson's chi-square test, which statistically assessed the significance of the observed differences.

Results. As part of the experimental study, a specially designed set of tasks and exercises focused on developing foreign language competence and delivered in a game-based format was piloted. The application of this set significantly improved the lexical and grammatical skills of third-grade students during foreign language learning and positively impacted the development of their communicative competence ($\chi^2 = 6.290$; $p < 0.05$).

Conclusion. The study confirmed that role-playing games, combining elements of realistic situations and gaming roles, create conditions for conscious and meaningful language acquisition, which is especially important for younger schoolchildren. The ability of role-play games to develop speaking skills, socio-communicative competences, and personal qualities in primary school students that makes the learning process more engaging and effective for children highlights the practical value of their usage.

KEYWORDS

role-playing game, foreign language instruction, younger schoolchildren, lexical-grammatical skills, foreign language competence, motivation

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INTRODUCTION

Foreign language education is an essential part of the modern world. It not only fosters communicative proficiency but also promotes intercultural exchange and the formation of a global civic identity. Learning foreign languages helps students develop the ability to communicate effectively in multilingual and multicultural environments.

UNESCO documents emphasize the importance of multilingual education based on instruction in the mother tongue and the gradual introduction of a second language. Foreign language learning is viewed as a condition for improving educational quality and promoting greater social inclusion [1].

International reports and agreements also highlight the growing need for communication in multilingual contexts, making foreign language acquisition strategically important for economic and cultural development. Educational systems worldwide are expected to integrate foreign languages at all levels of instruction and ensure conditions for their effective mastery across all age groups [2].

The significance of foreign language education, which is a compulsory subject from the 2nd to 11th grades is stated in the Federal State Educational Standard for Basic General Education. Foreign language classes are present at all schooling levels: primary, general, and secondary. Foreign language education aims at forming students' communicative competence, including its speaking, linguistic, sociocultural, compensatory, and metacognitive components. The Standard regards foreign language education as a key element in students' personal, communicative, and sociocultural development, aimed at their successful integration into today's multilingual and multicultural world [3].

To sum up, the importance of integrating foreign language instruction in early schooling with broader cultural and professional competencies is defined by national educational standards. We should highlight a communicative approach to language teaching, where the primary goal is to develop age-appropriate elementary communicative competence. Among effective pedagogical strategies, role-play stands out for its ability to enhance young learners' motivation, cognitive engagement, and creativity. By fostering an active and stimulating learning environment, play-based and communicative activities support conscious and meaningful language acquisition in primary school classes.

The aim of our study is to investigate and analyze role-play as an effective means of enhancing motivation and improving the quality of foreign language acquisition among primary school students.

Research objectives include:

- analyzing theoretical foundations and methodological approaches to using role-play in foreign language education for primary school students;
- examining the specific features and applications of role-play in developing various language skills (speaking, listening, reading, writing);
- designing and piloting a set of role-play activities adapted for primary school children;
- evaluating the effectiveness of role-play in developing communicative competence and enhancing linguistic activity in foreign language classes;
- identifying conditions that facilitate the successful implementation of role-play in the classroom.

SOURCES OVERVIEW

If education is viewed as a process of developing skills necessary for success in personal, professional, and social spheres, then foreign language competence emerges as a key determinant of successful adaptation and self-realization in the context of modern globalization and integration. A distinctive feature of foreign language learning is its broad educational and pedagogic impact, which extends beyond purely linguistic training [4, p. 233].

E.G. Tareva and B.V. Tarev believe that the foundational principles of modern linguodidactics are currently undergoing a deep reassessment under the influence of external factors and paradigmatic shifts in scientific knowledge [5]. In today's rapidly changing world, the search for new language

teaching methodologies has become increasingly urgent, marking a period of intensive exploration and implementation of innovative approaches aimed at effectively developing foreign language competence.

S.V. Merzlyakov notes that rapidly evolving political, economic, and social conditions impose new demands on the entire education system as well as on foreign language teaching in particular. A crucial aspect is the modernization of pedagogical approaches and the refinement of teaching methods, tools, and formats to enhance the effectiveness and quality of foreign language instruction. This reorientation aims not only to develop linguistic competencies of students but also communicative, cognitive, and sociocultural ones, reflecting the integrative nature of contemporary language education [6, p. 277].

Traditional teaching methods are no longer sufficient to meet the demands of the digital age and globalization, which call for personalized, interactive, and adaptive approaches. Traditional foreign language instruction often leads to decreased student motivation, as the material may seem to students neither new nor interesting. However, caution is needed when introducing new practices; teachers should examine both theoretical and practical materials, because certain difficulties can arise concerning different issues [7].

Foreign language teaching practices, while sharing common features with general education approaches, also possess unique characteristics stemming from the need to immerse learners in a symbolic and semiotic system distinct from their native language. Foreign language education is now aimed no longer at mastering some rules of a language. Communicative competence, critical thinking, and cultural awareness are today in the focus of teaching foreign languages. Ju. Waddington also emphasizes the need to cultivate self-reflection skills alongside linguistic and didactic competencies in English language teaching [8].

New realities demand new approaches to organizing the learning process, which is becoming the subject of study by scientists from various fields of scientific knowledge: pedagogy, sociology, psychology, linguistics. Contemporary challenges, especially those involving complex real-world problems, require education systems to create conditions for learners to acquire new competencies aligned with the needs of modern society [9]. D. Gillespie in the research draws on the concept of cultural immersion and analyzes the necessity of integrating contemporary sociocultural realities into the educational process [10].

The search and implementation of innovative methods in teaching foreign languages is becoming a key condition for successful language training in the context of global digital transformation and changing educational demands. Among the new trends in 2025 are the following: the use of artificial intelligence to personalize the learning process [11], the use of chatbots [12], gamification as a way to increase student motivation [13], online-services for creating interactive learning materials and assignments [14], and others.

A.M. Guerrettaz explores new concepts in language education: 1) assemblage, 2) "grammar of action" and 3) "phenomenological activity". The concept of phenomenological activity is associated with the conscious perception and experience of linguistic phenomena that goes beyond simple cramming, and includes understanding the structure of language, its connection with thinking and culture, as well as the study of personal experience of interacting with the language [15].

Fairy tales are regarded by scholars as an effective didactic tool for developing initial reading skills in primary school students [16]. M.A. Ariyan investigates the use of plotlines as a methodological strategy to foster coherent and logically structured monologic speech in a foreign language [17].

Game-based technologies contribute to a positive emotional classroom atmosphere which is a key factor in enhancing foreign language acquisition. Special attention is paid to building trusting relationships between teachers and students, which reduces anxiety and supports successful learning [18]. A supportive psychological climate helps learners develop a sense of identity, achieve success, while forming a strong classroom community especially important in primary education [19]. A.A. Pecherkina also stresses the importance of preserving students' emotional well-being and maintaining a supportive classroom environment [20, p. 137]. Emotions enhance motivation, active engagement, and depth of language acquisition; therefore, the emotional dimension should be integrated into foreign language teaching methodology [21].

Special requirements are also placed on foreign language teachers who work with primary school students. They must possess specific qualities that enable them to organize instruction effectively and create a comfortable atmosphere for their students [22].

To effectively develop intercultural communication skills, students must be placed in communicative situations that are as close as possible to real-life contexts. This approach immerses students in authentic language scenarios oriented toward practical application of knowledge [23].

Many scholars highlight the significant role of play in foreign language learning. O.A. Merzlyakova argues that games, including role-plays, create conditions for modeling real-life situations, allowing learners not only to practice foreign language communication but also to develop critical thinking within the target language environment [4].

The psychological and pedagogical aspects of teaching English to young learners have been examined in many scientific works. The role of play in primary education has been studied by D.B. Elkonin, A.V. Konyshcheva, L.G. Fribus, and others.

Role-play supports one of the key principles of communicative language teaching which is situationality [24, p. 11]. Z. Botirova also emphasizes the necessity of using game-based methods in English language instruction to stimulate cognitive activity in primary school students. This approach enhances engagement and promotes active learning through the integration of activity-based and playful components [25].

Teachers, the direct participants in the educational process, also note that the main tasks in teaching primary school students are to create conditions for the full development of children, their mental activity and independence in the search for the ways to solve certain tasks. The game has a high potential for achieving these goals [26, p. 79].

M.V. Tkachenko and Yu.V. Aleeva state that playing games significantly increases the emotional dimension of learning, making each lesson more vivid and exciting. Role-playing also substantially improves knowledge retention and cultivates perseverance, aspiration for success, and other motivational qualities essential for adult life. Due to emotional engagement and practical orientation, playing games fosters a positive attitude toward the subject, activates speech production, and stimulates critical thinking [27]. Moreover, playing serves not only as a teaching method but also as a health-promoting tool [28].

Play is not just entertainment but a way to understand social reality, reflecting human activity, tasks, and interpersonal norms, as noted by D.B. Elkonin. He classified games into four types based on age stages: (1) subject-based, (2) subject-plot-based, (3) role-based, and (4) plot-role-based [29].

Researchers view role-play as a guided speaking activity designed to enhance speaking skills and build communicative ability [30].

Thus, the analysis scientific investigations highlight the significant impact of role-play activities in foreign language education in primary schools.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The effectiveness of using story-based role-playing in English classes for primary school students was assessed by analyzing the content of tasks in the English textbook for third grade ("Rainbow English" by O.V. Afanasyeva and I.V. Mikheeva, "Drofa" publishing house, in two parts).

In the course of analysis, it was necessary to determine whether a role-playing game was included in the curriculum, whether there were already ready-made role-playing games, and also to determine the frequency of story-role-playing tasks.

The thematic content of written and spoken activities aligns with educational and developmental aims which coincide with the students' interests. The topics included in the content are connected with the following issues: family and relatives, hobbies, places of living, health, countries and cities, etc.

The analysis of educational learning material revealed that role-play activities are almost entirely absent from the textbook. Only six role-playing tasks are included in it, unevenly distributed between units and failing to cover all necessary communicative spheres. Moreover, the Teacher's Book provides no descriptions or guidelines for implementing these activities.

Role-play tasks are not included in Units 1 and 7. In Unit 2 ("What We Like"), Exercise 5, Page 41 presents a role-play focused on practicing the verb "to see" in spoken English. Students are invited to take on the roles of Harry the Troll and Emily the Elf and tell what the characters see in the picture. The key type of speech activity is a monologue.

The last five sections offer story and role-playing tasks aimed at developing dialogic speech skills. The exercises from Units 3 to 6 focus on developing speaking and listening skills through role-playing and interactive tasks. For example, in Unit 3 ("What color?") students practice color vocabulary by role-playing as Sally and her relatives, asking and answering questions about the colors of new items. In Unit 5 ("Happy Birthday!") students listen to a dialogue and then perform it in pairs, practicing the question "How old are you?" In Unit 8 "Seasons and Month" students are asked to imagine how the people who arrived in Britain spell their names. Overall, these activities use role-play, pair work, and real-life contexts to practice key vocabulary and question forms related to colors, numbers, age, and professions.

The Workbook does not provide any role-playing activities.

In order to analyze the tasks for organizing a role-playing game in German lessons in primary school, the content of the textbook for comprehensive schools with in-depth study of the German language for the 3rd-grade "Wunderkinder" (authors O.L. Zakharova, K.R. Zoiner) was examined in the course of investigation.

It should be noted that the textbook, consisting of two parts, covers topics that meet the needs of primary school students and, in our opinion, meets their cognitive interest in the surrounding world: "The world around us", "At home", "My loved ones", "A person can do anything", "Time", "My dreams", "In the woods and at home," "I love books." In the 3rd grade children learn to talk about their family, tell the time in German, describe the daily routine; talk about their hobbies, wild and domestic animals; read tourist brochures, fairy tales and German children's stories, and much more.

Thus, during the school year in the 3rd grade, children study eight topics. Role-play activities are absent only in Unit 2 ("Zu Hause überall"). There is one role-playing game in four topics: topic 1 "Die Welt ist groß" (Page 34 in the Unit "Denkland"), topic 6 "Traumwelt" (Page 44, Exercise 19), topic 7 "In the Forest and at home" (Page 80, in the Unit "Denkland"), topic 8 "Ich mag Bücher" (Page 92, Exercise 15).

Topic 4 "Was Menschen alles können" contains nine role-playing games (Page 100, Exercise 17; Page 100-101, Exercises 18, 19; Page 106, Exercise 28; Page 107, Exercise 30; Page 110, Exercise 36; Page 111, Exercise 38; Page 111, Exercise 38; Page 120, Exercise 4; Page 128, in the Unit "Denkland").

In each activity students are invited to make out a dialogue between fictional characters: animals (Lerny, Ellie, Foni, Vashi), people (Masha, Julian), actors (Karelia, Aibolit, Alfabeto), fairy Frida and students. The topics of the conversations include both the explanation of grammar structures, as well as conversations with a doctor or a salesperson.

To examine how teachers and students perceive the effectiveness of role-play in foreign language teaching, a survey was conducted among the teachers of Secondary School No. 8 (Yelets, Lipetsk Region) and Dolgorukovo Lyceum (Dolgorukovo, Lipetsk Region), and undergraduates of the Institute of Philology and Intercultural Communication (Bunin Yelets State University). The survey included 20 foreign language teachers and 40 university students.

90% of the surveyed teachers emphasized that such games perform a learning function, develop interest in the subject, communication skills, as well as monologue and dialogue speech. 75% of the students identified cognitive function, increased motivation, and the development of communication and social skills. They also highlighted that role-playing helps teachers organize lessons, involving all children.

100% of the teachers used role-playing games in their lessons, 90% tried to conduct them once a term, and 10% tried to do it once a week. The method is more often used in Grades 2-4. The students stated the difficulties of organizing role-playing games at the lesson due to the limited time, preferring to spend full games outside the learning process, using game elements in the lessons.

Preparing games, both teachers and students use elements of clothing, objects to create a setting, decorations, dolls and presentations. Praise and small prizes are often used to motivate primary school students.

The overall assessment of the importance of role-playing games is high: 50% of the surveyed teachers and 70% of the surveyed students consider them necessary, especially for the development of conversational speech, communication skills and immersion in the language environment. Games reduce the fear of mistakes and help children get used to using a foreign language in real communication situations.

The main challenges are the aesthetic and methodological base, organizational and technical limitations, as well as lack of time at the lessons.

The psychological qualities that this type of game develops, according to the teachers, include imagination, attentiveness, perseverance, speech, creative thinking, sociability, responsiveness, mutual understanding, willingness to cooperate and teamwork. The students add that role-playing is rather important for increasing the level of schoolchildren’s responsibility, independence, memory, striving for learning new things, developing communication and leadership skills.

Thus, the results of the survey confirm the relevance of our research.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK WITH THE 3RD-GRADE STUDENTS

In order to investigate the potential for actively employing story-based role-play to develop lexical and grammatical speaking abilities and overcome language barriers, an experiment was conducted among third-grade students in secondary schools in the Lipetsk region during the second term of the 2024–2025 school year. The researchers made the decision to involve students who study not only English but also German in the experiment. As a result, control and experimental groups were formed consisting of 27 participants each, with both groups including students who studied English and German. The overall number of participants in the experiment was 54.

Through the use of a didactic test, the initial proficiency level of third graders in speaking skills was identified. Eight written tasks were offered in English and German. Table 1 presents the ratio of criteria, indicators, descriptions of the test tasks and their scores.

Table 1 Criteria, indicators, description of tasks, didactic tests and their evaluation in points

Criterion	<i>Cognitive</i>	
Indicator	<i>The skills to ask questions (1)</i>	
Description of the tasks	Choose the appropriate question word from the given ones.	
Evaluation in points	1 point for each correct sentence. The maximum number of points is 5.	
Language	English	German
	1...are you? 2...do you come from? 3...is your name? 4...do you live with? 5...do you go to school? a)What b)Who c)how d)When e)Where	1....alt bist du? 2....kommst du? 3....wohnt in Berlin? 4....liegt das? 5....möchtest du? a) Wo b)Woher c)Wie d)Wer e)Was

Criterion	<i>Cognitive</i>	
Indicator	<i>The skills to ask questions (2)</i>	
Description of the tasks	Make an interrogative sentence using the given words.	
Evaluation in points	1 point for each correct sentence. The maximum number of points is 3.	
Language	English	German
	1) this, color, what, is? 2) English, can, speak, you,? 3) Tom, where, Nick, are, and?	1) hat, was, gern, Familie Wunderkind, gemacht? 2) es, gibt, eine Schule hier? 3) was, du, findest, in Marburg, interessant?
Criterion	<i>Cognitive</i>	
Indicator	<i>The skills to ask questions (3)</i>	
Description of the tasks	Choose questions from the given ones matching to the following answers.	
Evaluation in points	1 point for each correct question choice. The maximum number of points is 3.	
Language	English	German
	<i>Sentences:</i> 1)Pete 2)Eleven 3)It's two o'clock in the afternoon. <i>Questions:</i> 1)What time is it now? 2)How old are you? 3)What's his name?	<i>Sentences:</i> 1.Ein Kino. 2.Dort, an der Ecke. 3. Nein, falsch! Das ist ein Kino! <i>Questions:</i> 1.Ist das ein Museum? 2.Was ist das? 3.Wo ist hier ein Cafe?
Criterion	<i>Activity-based (1)</i>	
Indicator	<i>The ability to determine the logic of the narrative.</i>	
Description of the tasks	Combine the dialogical units given in an arbitrary sequence into a dialogue.	
Evaluation in points	2 points for choosing the correct sequence of sentences. The maximum number of points is 2.	
Language	English	German
	- Where does Sarah live? In a castle? - Exactly! I live there. - O! No, she lives in a flat. - And where do you live? In a house?	- Wo wohnt Nastja? In einem Schloss? - Genau! Ich wohne dorthin. - O! Nein, sie wohnt in einem Hochhaus. - Und wo wohnst du? In einem Reihenhaus?
Criterion	<i>Activity-based (2)</i>	
Indicator	<i>The ability to choose the right word. Choosing the right behavior model in different communication situations.</i>	
Description of the tasks	Restore the dialog by filling in the missing phrases	
Evaluation in points	1 point for each correct sentence. The maximum number of points is 3.	
Language	English	German
	1. -Julian, ... is this the living room? -On the ground floor. 2. -Nastya, will ...come with me to the garden? - With great pleasure! 3. -In the first...there is a dining room. - Let's get there together.	1. -Julian, ... ist hier das Wohnzimmer? -Im Erdgeschoss. 2. -Nastja, kommst ...mit mir in den Garten? - Mit großem Vergnügen! 3. -Im ersten...gibt es ein ein Esszimmer. - Kommen wir zusammen dorthin.
Criterion	<i>Activity-based (3)</i>	
Indicator	<i>The ability to choose the right word. Choosing the right behavior model in different communication situations.</i>	
Description of the tasks	Choose the dialog corresponding to the picture	
Evaluation in points	1 point for the correct choice of an advisory dialogue or congratulations. The maximum number of points is 4.	

Language	English	German
4	1. -Sorry! Tell me, please, how much does it cost? -Five euros. 2. -Hello, Jane! -Hello, Pete! 3. -Good morning, Mrs. Smith! - Good morning, kids! 4. -Hi! This car is super! How much does it cost?	1. -Entschuldigung! Sagen Sie bitte, was kostet es? - Fünf Euro. 2. -Hallo, Andreas! -Hallo, Klaus! 3. -Guten Morgen, Frau Müller! -Guten Morgen, Kinder! 4. Hallo! Dein Auto ist super! Und was kostet es?
Criterion	<i>Activity-based (4)</i>	
Indicator	<i>Choosing the right behavior model in different communication situations.</i>	
Description of the tasks	Choose the appropriate wishes for the situation greeting postcard.	
Evaluation in points	1 point for choosing the appropriate greeting card correctly. The maximum number of points is 4.	
Language	English	German
4	1. Happy New Year! 2. My best wishes for your birthday! 3. Be healthy and happy! 4. Have a good Easter!	1. Glücklichen Rutsch ins Neujahr! 2. Meine besten Wünsche zu Deinem Geburtstag! 3. Seien Sie gesund und glücklich! 4. Ein frohes Osterfest!
Criterion	<i>Activity-based (5)</i>	
Indicator	<i>The skills to conduct a conversation</i>	
Description of the tasks	Answer the interlocutor's questions correctly.	
Evaluation in points	2 points for each correct answer. The ability to use introductory phrases is considered (of course, unfortunately, with pleasure, by no means, however and others). The maximum number of points is 6.	
Language	English	German
	- What is your hobby? - Do you do sports? - Can you play the violin?	- Was machst du gern? - Treibst du gern Sport? - Kannst du Geige spielen?

Three levels of students' speaking skills were identified: high (24-30 points), medium (16-23 points), and low (less than 15 points).

The formative stage of the experimental work consisted in the assumption that the use of a story role-playing game in each lesson can ensure the effective formation of speaking skills of third grade students. In the conditions of digitalization of education, teachers are expanding the range of pedagogical tools for their development, selection and application.

In accordance with the third grade curriculum, during the experiment, students were offered tasks to practice clichés, the ability to ask questions, and respond to cues by using introductory words (in German, also (so), meiner Meinung nach (in my opinion), zuerst (at first), ehrlich gesagt (honestly), außerdem (in addition), allerdings (however), zum Beispiel (for example) and others; in English – so, to my mind (in my opinion), at first (firstly), frankly speaking (honestly), besides, however, for example, and others). In addition, the ability to use non-verbal signals to maintain contact with the interlocutor was formed.

Taking into account the age of the students, various games were offered for the formation and development of dialogical speech skills, which we consider to be the preparation for conducting a story-role-playing game (Table 2).

Table 2 Games for the formation and improvement of dialogic speech skills at foreign language lessons

Object of the game	Course of the game
Revising the word order in a German/ English sentence	Students get flashcards with written words. The task is to make different types of sentences: narrative with a direct and reverse word order and interrogative with and without a question word. You can organize two teams and give the same task. The team that makes up the sentences quickly and correctly wins.
Developing the skill of conducting spontaneous dialogues	1. Students get flashcards with questions of different levels of difficulty. They pick cards and answer the questions or ask each other, which leads to spontaneous conversation.
	2. Each person is to tell three things about themselves, two of which are true and one is fake. The others have to guess which one is fake by asking questions. Teachers can make the game more complicated by using German words like "ohne Zweifel", "zweifellos", "wahrscheinlich", "vermutlich", "übrigens", "im übrigen", "genau so" and English: "no doubt", "undoubtedly", "perhaps", "probably", "likely", "but", "then", "quite so".
	3. One of the students leaves the classroom. At this time, the rest of the students are making up questions for him. The player returns and truthfully answers the questions of the students except one question. The students must guess which question was answered incorrectly.

During the control phase of the experiment, a repeated assessment of the development of speaking skills in foreign language classes was conducted using the same methodology. Following this, the outcomes of the control and initial stages were compared, and the efficacy of the experimental approach was determined using the Pearson χ^2 test.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The ascertaining stage of the experiment showed the presence of students with high, medium and low levels of speaking.

Children with a high level of communication skills demonstrated good knowledge of grammar, the ability to apply grammatical rules in a new communicative situation, and the ability to compose simple narrative and interrogative sentences. They used the necessary lexical units as well as non-verbal communication methods.

Students with a medium level of proficiency in speaking skills made inaccuracies when using colloquial clichés. In addition, there were minor errors in the order of words in simple narrative and interrogative sentences. These inaccuracies could have been corrected by the teacher's leading questions.

Third grade students with a low level of speaking skills made many mistakes when composing narrative and interrogative sentences. They had difficulty choosing words and colloquial clichés.

Diagram 1 shows the test results in the control and experimental groups.

The lack of significant differences between the two groups was confirmed by using the Pearson chi-squared test, with a degree of freedom of 2. The calculated chi-squared value was 0.186, which is less than the critical value of 5.991 at a significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the differences in the distributions of the variables between the experimental and control groups are not statistically significant, and there is no evidence to suggest that the treatments had an impact on the outcome.

Diagram 1 The results of the ascertaining experiment

Diagram 2 The results of the control experiment

The findings from the control phase of the study supported the efficacy of the consistent implementation of story-driven role-play in each class session in the experimental groups. As illustrated in Diagram 2, there was a notable predominance in the number of participants exhibiting medium and high levels of proficiency, when compared to the control group. The analysis of the Pearson χ^2 statistic revealed a statistically significant correlation between the factorial and performance parameters, with a degree of freedom of 2. The calculated value of χ^2 is 6.290, while the critical value is 5.991, corresponding to a significance level of $p < 0.05$, with $p = 0.044$.

Thus, the series of narrative role-playing games we have developed and tested in the course of teaching a foreign language to third-graders has proven its efficacy.

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

In modern times, special attention is paid in pedagogical circles to the development of students' competencies. As for the process of teaching foreign languages, first of all, we are talking about the development of communicative competencies. A foreign language is an ideal subject for teaching

students the rules of communication, as all types of speech activity develop in the learning process, namely, reading, writing, listening and speaking. In this regard, role-playing is one of the most effective methods of teaching communication skills in a foreign language. In addition to achieving direct learning goals, students' cognitive interest is developed while role-playing, their creative activity manifests itself, teamwork skills improve, and motivation to learn foreign languages and the learning process as a whole increases.

We agree with the authors F. Liu, B. Vadivel, E. Rezvani and E. Namaziadost [31] that by organizing children's participation in a role-playing game, the teacher simulates real communication situations, which in the future will help students in the process of social adaptation to adulthood. During the game, children's personal qualities are developed, for example, sociability, quick-wittedness, resourcefulness. Trying to succeed in the game, children forget about the fear of making mistakes, which has a beneficial effect on the learning outcomes planned by the teacher.

Any teacher who knows the methodology of teaching foreign languages rather well must first think through all the stages of the plot-role game, the distribution of roles, props, the lexical minimum for communication, and criteria for evaluating students' speech actions. The game should not be interrupted to correct errors, as this will disrupt the gameplay. The teacher fixes mistakes in his students' speech, but he will correct them after the end of the game while giving some special tasks. The data we have obtained is completely consistent with the opinion of T. Ravshanova, R. Karshieva, M. Kuvvatov who draw attention to the fact that the types of role-playing games can be different depending on the level complexity and language skills of students [32].

The lexical and grammatical foreign language material intended for consolidation in the course of game actions should be within the capabilities of schoolchildren. As a rule, role-playing games can be conducted at the final lesson of some lexical topic to improve students' foreign language lexical and grammatical skills. This aligns with the points of view of S. Vićević Ivanović, N. Košuta and J. Patekar [33]. They studied young learners' language learning strategies using Croatian as an example and proved the effectiveness of role-playing in this respect. The researchers Ch.-J. Lin, G.-J. Hwang, Q.-K. Fu, Ya.-H. Cao analyze the means of facilitating EFL students' English grammar learning performance and behaviors in the framework of contextual gaming approach [34] that is in accordance with our work.

A survey of the opinions of foreign language teachers and students regarding the use of role-playing games in the process of learning foreign languages showed that almost they all use them in their professional activities and consider them a necessary and important means of improving the educational process. Game plots at foreign language lessons make it possible to diversify traditional teaching methods, increase the interest and motivation of students to achieve more successful learning outcomes, and create a unique atmosphere of immersion in the language environment. However, M.R. Urazova [35] pays more attention to using digital innovative technologies in teaching and studying English than to including role-playing games into the lesson. Gh.G. Thompson, S.V. Gillern study the importance of video-game instruction for vocabulary acquisition with English language learners [36] and the authors Y. Ma, Y. Wang, M. Fleeer, L. Li focus their attention on using conceptual PlayWorld as a new play practice [37].

In the course of the study, we analyzed the English and German language curriculum for the third grade of general education institutions. It turned out that the authors offered to use some game tasks in teaching foreign languages, but their number is clearly insufficient, given the advantages of these methods that we have identified. Younger students can improve their foreign language speaking skills without realizing it, but simply by participating in role-playing games, of course, under the guidance and supervision of their teacher.

Despite the popularity and demand of modern information technologies in the educational process, based on the analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature on the research topic and the data obtained, we believe that the use of story-role-playing games in teaching foreign languages at school, especially in elementary grades, allows students to improve their communication skills, create real communication conditions, and develop their personal to increase interest in the study of this academic subject and to strengthen motivation for the educational process as a whole.

CONCLUSION

Thus, summing up all the above, it can be noted that role-playing is not an auxiliary, but one of the effective methods in the process of teaching foreign languages to primary school students. It meets age requirements, develops communicative competence and forms stable motivation. However, for maximum effectiveness, a systematic, thoughtful and differentiated approach to using role-playing games is required, taking into account not only linguistic goals, but also psychological, social and cultural aspects of the child's development.

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